

The experience of foreign countries in improving the activities of auxiliary enterprises in military units

Mullayev Baxtiyor Yaxyoyevich

*Public Safety University of the Republic of Uzbekistan
graduate student*

[*mullayevbaxtiyor7@gmail.com*](mailto:mullayevbaxtiyor7@gmail.com)

Abstract: this article examines the experience of foreign countries in improving the activities of auxiliary farms in military units. In addition, the role and importance of the military industrial complex in the development of the military sector is highlighted. In particular, the experience of Russia and the USA, as well as information on the article from leading countries such as Germany, France, and China are presented.

Key words: subsidiary economy, military-industrial complex, innovative development, small innovative enterprises, industrial-innovative cluster.

The military-industrial complex (DIC) enterprises have a great role for the country's economy, because these enterprises preserved their scientific potential and production capacity during the difficult period of transition from the administrative economy to the market economy, which allows them today. production of highly competitive products in world markets.

At the current stage of development, defense industry enterprises receive very strong support from the state in the form of state defense orders as part of the program of rearmament of the country's army. This program has ultimate goals and outcomes. By 2020, directing defense industry enterprises to the production of civilian products is one of these goals, therefore, the experience of foreign countries in establishing mutually beneficial cooperation between defense industry enterprises and small innovative enterprises is of great interest. is shooting Such cooperation allows using the main resources of enterprises and organizations to create competitive high-tech products both in the arms market and in the civilian product market. It is also important to determine the conditions for the effectiveness of such interaction in the country's economy.

National defense, from the point of view of economic theory, production, as we know it, refers to the pure public goods that the state undertakes. However, the components of the defense complex are created both by state commercial and non-commercial enterprises, and by private enterprises, including small innovative enterprises. At the same time, it is of great interest to study the innovative component of defense production and the impact of this component on the innovative processes of the entire economy. Because it is an innovative component that allows countries to compete with each other in global arms markets and has a diffusion effect on other sectors of the economy.

The modern economy is characterized by the development of the global arms market, which shows very stable development indicators - the share of military expenditures in the world GDP varies at the level of 2.3-2.6%, the accumulated experience in creating a competitive product, which ensures stability. financial stability of the main players in the international arms market.

According to the Stockholm Peace Research Institute, the main countries leading the arms market in 2015 are the USA - 33%, Russia - 25%, China - 5.9%. The United States of America and Russia have long occupied the first places in the world ranking of major arms exporters. However, if the US arms market share increased from 29% to 33% in 2009-2015, Russia would

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lose its market share from 27% to 25% during the same period. Germany and France, which until recently held the third and fourth places in terms of arms exports, are giving way to China.

The United States occupies a leading position in the arms market, because there is a NATO bloc under the auspices of this country, and accordingly, the US spending on military needs in this bloc was 72.2% in 2015].

The experience of the impact of the US military-industrial complex on innovation processes

It is known that the United States has created an effective system of cooperation between the enterprises of the military-industrial complex and business structures, which can be considered "classic". Such a system began to take shape in the 30s of the 20th century and continued after the Second World War, in which loans were given to open companies for social purposes only, to rehabilitate ex-servicemen and return them to a peaceful life. to serve in the army. Later, a special department for financing and investment activities was established in the administration of the President of the USA, and its functions were significantly expanded. It began working as a prime contractor on federal contracts to supply goods and services to the military, contracts awarded to small businesses.

Maintaining the technological superiority of the US armed forces, preventing the sudden emergence of new technical means of armed warfare for the US, supporting advanced research and bridging the gap between basic research and its military application for the US Department of Defense (US Department of Defense) is conducting research that is divided into two main groups:

1. Internal R&D conducted in defense research laboratories (Livermore Laboratory, Los Alamos National Laboratory, Lincoln Laboratory, US Army Research Center, etc.);
2. "External" scientific and research work conducted in corporations, universities, small innovative enterprises, sometimes in cooperation with defense laboratories.

Accordingly, the implemented scientific projects have three directions:

- fundamental projects, as a rule, are financed by universities;
- practical research, often a continuation of basic research that is fully compatible with defense tasks; these studies, as a rule, are financed by enterprises of the military-industrial complex, with which the university can be a partner;
- practical research, at the stage of which the development has a special military application and has been tested. This type of work is usually carried out by the enterprise, sometimes in cooperation with a potential operational service.

The Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) has been established under the US Department of Defense to carry out fundamental research, and it actively works with US universities. This interaction is related to the institutional characteristics of the concentration of scientific and research personnel in large developed universities in the United States, which is significantly different from, for example, Russia, where the concentration of scientific personnel in specialized research centers prevails. , which does not always combine scientific and educational potential (in the Russian Federation, an exception to the rule may be the Novosibirsk academic town, where, along with educational institutions, scientific institutes are concentrated, where students do internships, etc.).

With the financial support of DARPA, scientific and research work is carried out not only on military issues, but also on bilateral technologies. Thus, in the organization of the work of the Internet, in the production of semiconductors and integrated components, there are developments carried out with the direct participation of DARPA.

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In addition to purely defense research funding, which accounted for 18% of DARPA's budget expenditures in 2011, materials and biotechnology (~10.1% of the budget), advanced aerospace systems (9.8% of the budget), and electronics technology (~9.2% of the budget).

This type of cooperation between the state, business and science is beneficial for all parties. The first party receives its military orders using the latest, state-of-the-art technology. The second is to re-equip the material and technical base at the expense of loans, and will have the opportunity to conduct scientific research, and the third is to attract talented students to scientific research in close cooperation with business, and then they will have the opportunity to become employees of large enterprises. owners of concerns or small small enterprises implementing innovative developments. In addition, small innovative companies make it possible to obtain high-quality services/products at an acceptable price-quality ratio.

In the global innovation index published in 2015, the United States is ranked 5th, Russia is 48th, and Switzerland is leading.

As noted by the co-author of the lecture and the head of the deanery. Ann and Elmer Lindseth Graduate School of Management. Samuel Curtis Johnson at Cornell University, "Quality of innovation matters. Building top-notch universities and investing in research is critical to continuing to lead the global race for successful innovation."

The Russian defense industry occupies a special place in the structure of the national economy. It is the most competitive part of the non-resource sector of the economy, solves the problems of creation and production of modern types of weapons and military equipment, meets the needs of the civil industry for high-tech products that require knowledge. despite this, the defense industry is the only production industry capable of solving many technological problems at the level of modern requirements. Currently, according to the information of the Interdepartmental Analytical Center, more than 70 percent of all scientific products produced in our country are contributed by the defense industry, more than 50 percent of all scientific workers are employed in the defense industry. and can play an important role in ensuring the new quality and pace of development of the country's economy as a whole.

The regions least affected by the current economic situation, as noted in the report of N. Zubarevich, director of the regional program of the Independent Social Policy Institute, "Crisis in Russia - regional forecast: what to expect and what to prepare for." The crisis in Russia is the agro-industrial sector, the regions where oil and gas enterprises are located, as well as the regions where there are enterprises of the defense industry. Because these enterprises are strongly supported by the state in the modern economic reality.

According to RINCCE, a scientific research institute of the Federal State Budgetary Institution, the costs of technological innovations are mainly financed from the state budget, and the volume of these costs is increasing every year.

There is a clear trend of reduction in the amount of own funds of organizations allocated to financing technological innovations - from 79.9 percent in 2005 to 51 percent in 2014. activities related to the use of computing and information technologies, scientific research and development decreased from 88.6 percent in 2005 to 26.2 percent in 2014, budget funds for these purposes increased from 0.7 percent in 2005 to 55.4 percent in 2014 appeared. Of course, part of these funds was directed to defense industry enterprises.

With an appropriate, functioning mechanism of interaction between defense industry enterprises and small innovative enterprises, which can also be created in universities, a

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sufficiently high diffusion effect can be obtained for the development of the entire national economy.

For this, there are all internal incentives for defense industry enterprises, which should increase the volume of civilian products by 30% by 2015 and by 2020. But as M. Remizov, president of the National Strategy Institute, noted at the roundtable discussion "Growth points of the regional economy: the interaction of the defense industry and small and medium-sized enterprises", held on May 25, 2016 in Voronezh - "We (in the defense industry) have established a price system that does not always encourage savings; it is profitable. Invest more. And this is unacceptable in the civilian market." Therefore, attracting small/medium innovative businesses it is vital not only for defense industry enterprises, but also for the economy as a whole. It is defense industry enterprises that can and should involve small enterprises in the implementation of the state defense order (SDO) for the fulfillment of orders - all the organizational and legal mechanisms for this are in place, which strengthen cooperative relations. Create less painful conditions for the transition of defense industry enterprises to the production of civilian products by 2020 d. In addition, such cooperation increases the competitiveness of the civil sector of the engineering industry, which is known to have a high multiplier effect.

Such cooperation is possible in the conditions of subcontracting, outsourcing, business incubation and innovation cluster (industrial-innovation cluster).

In our opinion, the most successful option for cooperation is an industrial-innovative cluster, which includes small innovative enterprises, including enterprises established on the basis of leading specialized universities and parent enterprises of the defense industry, which confirms the experience of successful countries. High results in adapting the defense industry to market conditions, the first general US experience.

The clustering effect is formed by optimizing the costs of parent enterprises by transferring high-risk innovative projects to small enterprises. Small innovative enterprises are more adapted to such activities if they have the core competencies of personnel, technology and equipment specialized in research activities.

In recent years, the Russian state has paid enough attention to the development of industrial policy, including the defense industry. A number of regulatory and legal documents aimed at activating these processes have been adopted. The main ones are: the national standard of the Russian Federation 56425-2015; Resolution No. 1119 of the Government of the Russian Federation; Federal Law No. 488-FZ of December 31, 2014; Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation dated July 31, 2015 No. 779 and others.

In modern conditions, the considered mechanism does not work very effectively, because, as experts have pointed out, there are a number of specific features in the relationship between defense industry enterprises and small/medium businesses. First, the conditions for organizing and accepting jobs in the defense industry are stricter. The second is the existence of state secrets and the need to create such working conditions for their preservation. The third feature is that large concerns tend to buy small innovative businesses or outgrow a specialist who is engaged in the necessary development.

In addition, the creation of clusters for the simple use of budget funds often leads to their inefficient use and the manifestation of the element of corruption in the defense industry.

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The above characteristics of cooperation are determined by the shortcomings of legal regulation and, among other things, the specific characteristics of licensing activities of SMEs engaged in innovative developments in the field of weapons and military equipment (WME). Federal Law No. 275-FZ of December 29, 2012 "On the Order of State Defense" defines the requirements for the initial qualification of participants (qualification requirements, experience in providing defense and security needs, financial limitations), which are small organizations will be beyond their capabilities. enterprises. Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation dated June 13, 2012 No. 581 "Licensing the development, production, testing, installation, assembly, maintenance, repair, disposal and sale of weapons and military equipment" The decision "on" significantly limits the participation of small and medium-sized business entities. State defense order (GOZ) due to a large number of requirements, for example, ownership of property (equipment) to carry out activities, having the right to carry out activities related to the use of information included in state secrets (in cases provided for by the rules). legislation of the Russian Federation) and others.

These regulations contradict the decision of the Government of the Russian Federation dated July 31, 2015 No. 779 "On Industrial Clusters and Specialized Organizations of Industrial Clusters". state defense order.

Federal Law No. 275-FZ "On State Defense Order" No. 44-FZ "On State Defense Order" "Contract system in the field of procurement of goods, works, services meeting state requirements" Similar to the law on ", it is necessary to make changes on the participation of small and medium-sized enterprises in the state defense order. and municipal needs", as well as to reduce licensing requirements for small and medium-sized businesses in the field of weapons and military equipment, but not to harm the security of the country. That is, in accordance with the innovative development strategy of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2020, adopted in 2011, it is necessary to eliminate norms that hinder technological development and do not ensure increased safety.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that a very successful experience of cooperation between small innovative business and enterprises of the military-industrial complex, in particular the USA, has been accumulated. In the post-restructuring economy of the country, it was the defense industry enterprises that managed to preserve their innovative potential, which allows them to maintain one of the leading positions in the world arms market. In modern conditions, innovation processes occur faster, so there is a need to quickly adapt defense industry enterprises to market conditions. The state industrial policy directs defense industry enterprises to cooperate with small innovative enterprises and institutions, which allows them to solve scientific and technical problems, increase their efficiency and maintain competitiveness. However, the existing mechanism of cooperation between small innovative and defense industry enterprises does not give the desired results. Therefore, in the current institutional environment where it is necessary to eliminate legal conflicts, there is a need to improve the mechanism of encouraging cooperation of the parties aimed at mutually beneficial cooperation.

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